

The Necessity of Dynamic Workflow Managers for Advancing Self-driving Labs and Optimizers

Simon K. Steensen Patrick W. V. Butler Jesper R. Pedersen Nis Fisker-Bødker Tejs Vegge Jin Hyun Chang Ivano E. Castelli

Simon K. Steensen

Technical University of Denmark, Department of Energy Conversion and Storage; Anker Engelunds Vej, Building 301, Kgs. Lyngby 2800, Denmark

Dr. Patrick W. V. Butler

Technical University of Denmark, Department of Energy Conversion and Storage; Anker Engelunds Vej, Building 301, Kgs. Lyngby 2800, Denmark

Jesper R. Pedersen

Technical University of Denmark, Department of Energy Conversion and Storage; Anker Engelunds Vej, Building 301, Kgs. Lyngby 2800, Denmark

Nis Fisker-Bødker

Technical University of Denmark, Department of Energy Conversion and Storage; Anker Engelunds Vej, Building 301, Kgs. Lyngby 2800, Denmark

Prof. Tejs Vegge

Technical University of Denmark, Department of Energy Conversion and Storage; Anker Engelunds Vej, Building 301, Kgs. Lyngby 2800, Denmark

Assoc. Prof. Jin Hyun Chang

Technical University of Denmark, Department of Energy Conversion and Storage; Anker Engelunds Vej, Building 301, Kgs. Lyngby 2800, Denmark

Prof. Ivano E. Castelli

Technical University of Denmark, Department of Energy Conversion and Storage; Anker Engelunds Vej, Building 301, Kgs. Lyngby 2800, Denmark

Email Address: ivca@dtu.dk

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In this work, we highlight the need for dynamic workflow managers in self-driving laboratories (SDLs) and optimizers for Materials Acceleration Platforms (MAPs). While MAPs leverage AI and automation to accelerate materials discovery, static workflow managers limit scalability and flexibility. We demonstrate the benefits of modular, adaptable orchestrators by integrating PerQueue, a dynamic workflow manager, into a color-mixing robot, streamlining task coordination and AI-driven optimization. Additionally, we assess various MAP-relevant methodologies based on their maturity and readiness for integration. This assessment underlines the importance of flexible workflow managers in advancing SDLs and optimizers, paving the way for more effective future MAP implementations. Achieving seamless integration requires addressing challenges like ensuring data provenance, adhering to FAIR principles, and adapting workflows to changing experimental conditions—key elements for the successful deployment of MAPs.

1 Introduction

To address the climate crisis and resource scarcity, the rapid development of advanced materials is essential for energy storage, clean energy technologies, and sustainable development [1]. A single research institution cannot alone solve the challenges that we are facing and achieve the ambitious goals of a World-wide net-zero future. This, however, can be more realistically pursued by developing a network of interconnected (national and international) laboratories, which in addition to sharing equipment and expertise need to agree upon common FAIR data infrastructure, ontologies, standards and protocols leading to interoperability of methodologies [2, 3, 4, 5]. The development of such an interoperable research infrastructure of modular infrastructures has its foundation in the fourth scientific paradigm of materials discovery—driven by big data analyzed by machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI)—offering a powerful framework for accelerating materials innovation [6]. This paradigm is embodied in

the concept of Materials Acceleration Platforms (MAPs) [7, 8], which apply these principles to expedite the development of advanced materials. This perspective highlights some of the key challenges in the development of MAPs by focusing on the advancement of self-driving labs (SDLs) and AI. We emphasize the importance of dynamic workflow managers as critical enablers of efficient, autonomous, and scalable MAPs. While SDLs and MAPs are sometimes used interchangeably, they refer to distinct but complementary concepts. SDLs are automated experimental platforms through utilization of robotics and often incorporate AI to autonomously plan, execute, and analyze experiments. MAPs, however, are integrated frameworks that leverage a comprehensive data infrastructure, often using ML and AI for prediction and property optimization. Note predefined MAPs with fixed decision rules based on outcomes can also be designed. Their methodologies vary depending on the optimization objective, often combining computational modeling and high-throughput experimentation, and even incorporating automation to enhance efficiency through SDLs [9, 10]. By integrating computational and experimental data across multiple fidelities and scales, MAPs enable simultaneous multi-objective optimization, accelerating materials discovery. However, large centralized MAPs are expensive and time-intensive to establish, leading to a shift toward the decentralized and asynchronous implementations [11, 12, 13]. Additionally, supporting this shift is the FINALES software [14] providing a modular API designed to facilitate distributed MAP architectures. Unlike centralized platforms [15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24], the decentralized approaches focus on delocalization of resources and decision-making agents, enabling collaboration between institutions across different geographical locations. This requires flexible and asynchronous communication designs, which accommodate varying methodological requirements and even logical constraints such as time zone differences. While decentralization fosters scientific progress through collaboration, it also shifts the reliance to local implementations, such as reliable SDLs that need to manage complex workflows to integrate seamlessly into the broader MAP framework.

Figure 1a illustrates a MAP design that incorporates theoretical modeling across different scales (atomistic and mesoscale) [25, 26], human-operated experiments, ML and statistics-based analytics, autonomous robotics, AI decision-making, digital twin tracking, and an ontologized and interoperable data infrastructure. Here, our assessment of the maturity level and readiness for MAP integration for each method is displayed by the colors surrounding the method: green signifies high readiness for deployment, yellow indicates methods possible to deploy though still undergoing refinement and improvement, while red represents low readiness, requiring significant development before integration. This perspective concerns the methods that are not yet at high readiness for deployment (the yellow and red).

Ontologized interoperable data infrastructure [27] is classified in low readiness (red), in part due to its reliance on ontologies in materials science, a relatively new area of study. Ontologies provide a structured, machine-readable framework for representing domain-specific knowledge by formally defining entities (classes), their attributes, and relationships between them—such as 'has-property' or 'is-a' hierarchies.

While standardized formats like OPTIMADE [28] facilitate syntactic interoperability and data exchange, ontologies go further by enabling semantic interoperability—capturing the meaning, context, and relationships between data elements. This deeper structuring allows for automated reasoning over materials data, hopefully enabling AI agents to infer missing information, detect inconsistencies, and even assist in hypothesis generation or synthesis planning—thereby transforming how materials research is conducted [29]. While materials science ontologies have been developed [30, 31, 32], they have not yet achieved widespread adoption within the community, limiting their integration into datasets. Broader acceptance would enable semantic querying and facilitate the efficient extraction of data points from combined datasets that meet specific criteria within archive-level graph databases.

Recently, ontologized data sets from a MAP optimization campaign were generated for the first time [33]. However, these were not integrated into the infrastructure but applied post hoc via scripting. As of now a coherent strategy for fully integrating ontologized, interoperable infrastructures into MAPs remains undeveloped.

AI-driven decision-making is a key enabler to fully utilize MAPs and has already been successfully implemented for guiding and optimizing experimental campaigns. However, for MAPs to reach their full

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: (a): Overview of a MAP integrating multiple methodologies, coordinated by a central broker server. The color-coded assessment indicates maturity and readiness for integration: green (well-established and ready for implementation), yellow (deployable but still under active development and evolution), and red (in early stages of development). Note that even methods marked green can still pose integration challenges; the colors serve as a general guide rather than a strict difficulty ranking. In the context of this perspective, workflow managers intersect with many of the individual methods present in the MAP, emphasizing that a dynamic workflow manager is crucial to fully realize the potential of methodologies such as self-driving laboratories (SDLs) and AI agents. (b): Assessment of general development aspects of workflow managers, with red indicating underdevelopment, yellow indicating partial or selective development, and green representing full maturity. Further development would be to advance the underdeveloped points so that the entire arrow shifts toward green.

potential, they must integrate multiple interdependent models and coordinate across decentralized SDLs, so these are classified as still needing refinement and development (yellow). While SDLs have already been deployed, their reliability and functionality still require further refinement. In the recent seminal paper [11], decentralized asynchronous SDLs were successfully applied to molecular synthesis and in-line property characterization for optimizing stimulated emission properties in thin-film devices. However,

the authors emphasize that future implementations should incorporate well-defined policies to ensure robustness and reproducibility—ideally through regularly scheduled control experiments with prior known outcomes. AI agents have also been implemented, as previously cited. For example, [12] demonstrated simultaneous multi-target optimization at both the material and device levels (targeting ionic conductivity and end-of-life performance in a battery cell) within the same MAP. To our knowledge, however, no existing implementation has yet achieved multi-objective optimization that coherently links atomistic or molecular descriptors with device-level metrics in a fully integrated loop. How to realize this remains a significant open challenge, necessitating advances in scalable, generalizable AI models and rigorous uncertainty quantification across scales. Note that addressing this challenge is not limited to the implementation of agents, it will also require the formulation of domain-specific hypotheses within the reach of MAPs’ capabilities.

Ensuring seamless orchestration of autonomous experiments, decision-making agents, and data infrastructures requires workflow management systems that are both flexible and scalable. While static workflow managers are constrained by predefined task graphs that cannot change during execution, a dynamic workflow manager is capable of modifying the workflow’s dependency graph during execution. This may involve adjusting the number of parallel jobs to submit based on intermediate outputs, submitting tasks in a cyclic loop until predefined criteria are met, or dynamically selecting which edge in the directed graph the workflow should follow next. Through altering workflow structures—such as queuing sub-workflows during execution (e.g. triggering a cyclic calibration workflow in response to sensor drift)—dynamic workflow managers support real-time adaptation to evolving experimental conditions, allowing SDLs to efficiently allocate resources, adjust workflows on-the-fly, and maintain robustness. Existing implementations often rely on rigid, predefined static workflows, limiting adaptability and making dynamic workflow managers essential for accelerating discovery while ensuring reliability and transparency.

2 Challenges in orchestrating decentralized self-driving labs

SDLs are rapidly advancing across scientific fields, enabling automated experimentation and accelerating discovery [10, 34, 35, 36]. To support decentralized and asynchronous experimentation, both data architecture and SDLs must transition from rigid, single-purpose implementation to modular and scalable systems [37, 38, 39]. Initial SDLs focused on automating specific tasks, evolving from early robotic systems [40, 41, 10]. Later *Cooper et al.* [42] integrated multiple instruments within a single laboratory setup. Such a system can utilize several workstations that hardly can be implemented within fixed flexible automation platforms like robotic arms. Currently the establishment of robust, distributed SDL networks facilitating collaboration between research groups is of interest [43]. The BIG-MAP project, for instance, demonstrates integration of several workflow engines into robotic platforms setups across institutions [44]. These coordinated and distributed systems are essential for executing complex experimental workflows and accelerating discovery, particularly relevant for new energy materials [45]. However, managing such distributed SDLs significantly increases workflow complexity, requiring adaptable software for workflow coordination. Traditional single-equipment automation, which relies on monolithic, sequentially programmed workflows, is insufficient for MAP-integrated environments. Instead, scalable and dynamic workflow managers are essential to advancing fully autonomous, interconnected laboratories.

The need for modular elements in SDLs is particularly evident in error-handling challenges. The complex orchestration of software and hardware in SDLs makes them susceptible to failures, including resource depletion (e.g., reagents, solvents), equipment malfunctions (e.g., lost connections, motor drift), and unexpected measurement values [38]. Without predefined error-handling mechanisms, workflows encountering such issues often abort and require manual intervention. Beyond operational efficiency, robust error handling is also critical for lab safety, ensuring that experiments return to a safe state when failures occur.

Decomposing workflows into modular tasks enables integrated error handling that responds dynamically to task outcomes. These modular error-handling routines can be reused and adapted to handle both re-

coverable and non-recoverable errors, such as redoing measurements, switching to an alternative sub-workflow, or triggering alerts to ensure safety. At initialization, the number of tasks produced by different task groups during a run is unknown, rendering a static workflow manager insufficient due to its lack of flexibility. A dynamic workflow can detect these anomalies and automatically repeat measurements a predefined number of times before proceeding, reducing the need for manual intervention.

With over 350 workflow managers available [46], each with distinct strengths and weaknesses, interoperability is crucial for ensuring scientific reproducibility. This diversity reflects the absence of a ‘one-size-fits-them-all’ solution—workflow managers are designed to address different needs based on local research context [47]. For SDLs, a workflow manager should support dynamic workflows, in contrast to the many static workflow engines available, which is generally underdeveloped in many workflow implementations as represented in Figure 1b. This allows for the execution of complex tasks while maintaining robustness against errors. The following demonstrator illustrates how dynamic workflows can simplify the setup and operation of SDLs, highlighting their potential for seamless automation.

3 Demonstrator: Orchestrated color-mixing robot using PerQueue

To demonstrate the application of dynamic workflows in SDLs, we used a color mixing platform capable of optimizing mixing ratios to match target colors. This platform is managed by PerQueue, a dynamic workflow manager designed to coordinate complex, modular tasks [48]. PerQueue is a Python-based workflow manager that supports the aforementioned dynamic capabilities—switching of task paths, cyclic task execution, and dynamic adjustment of parallel task groups—all within a lightweight architecture that is easily deployed with a simple Python script. As shown in Figure 2, the platform can dispense four colors (red, green, blue, and yellow) into a test cell via pumps. The color of the resulting mixture is measured using a color sensor illuminated by LEDs, which returns an RGB value corresponding to the input ratios. The optimization process begins with a target RGB value, and an algorithm iteratively adjusts mixing ratios to minimize the root mean square difference (RMSD) between the measured and target RGB values. The optimization is performed using the newly developed Odyssey software [49], a Python-based interface for Bayesian optimization (BO) methods that efficiently explore the parameter space to refine the mixing ratio.

During operation, PerQueue handles all communication between the robot and the optimizer. After measuring the target color and cleaning the test cell, the workflow enters a cyclical phase, where the optimizer proposes mixing ratios, which are then prepared and measured by the robot. The cyclic task continuously submits jobs until either the maximum number of iterations is reached or the RMSD between the target and measured colors falls below a predefined threshold value. Throughout the experiment, PerQueue orchestrates the execution of tasks and workflows, coordinating interactions between the optimizer, the robot, and data handling components. It schedules tasks such as prediction requests to Odyssey, experimental execution by the robot, and storage of the experimental data in the database, ensuring efficient workflow progression and task synchronisation. By separating the optimizer from the robot, PerQueue facilitates the automated data passing between components, which streamlines SDL experiments and allows researchers to focus on task implementation.

The color-mixing demonstration also revealed areas for improving PerQueue in SDL workflows and equipment interfacing. Unlike traditional workflows with sequential dependencies, SDL workflows often require long-range dependencies—for example, passing the target RGB value from the first to the final step to calculate the score. While such dependencies can be handled using log files and manual retrieval within the prompted scripts, integrating them directly into the workflow manager improves clarity and maintainability. This level of integration was not supported in MyQueue [50], from which PerQueue originated. Future improvements will focus on enabling direct interaction with robotic tasks, allowing users to pause or stop workflows without cancelling them entirely, allowing for human intervention or human-in-the-loop solutions [51] as highlighted in Figure 1b. These enhancements will further support distributed, asynchronous SDL workflows, increasing their flexibility and robustness.

Figure 2: Overview of demonstrator workflow. The **leftmost** box shows the high-level workflow, which consists of three main tasks: specifying the target color, resetting the robot, and executing a cyclic task group submitting jobs that runs the optimization until convergence. The **central** box details the individual tasks that are generated by the workflow, with robot tasks shown in dark green and Odyssey tasks in black. Tasks are numbered according to their execution order, with n incrementing per iteration of the cyclic loop. The **rightmost** column provides a graphical legend. The setup of the color-mixing robot is shown in the dark green box.

4 Outlook

The implementation of a dynamic workflow in the color-mixing platform demonstrates their potential to enhance the performance of SDLs. By leveraging PerQueue for task management and Odyssey for optimization, the platform simplifies experimentation, enabling more efficient iterative processes with easier development and more reusable code. Separating the optimizer from robot control facilitates easy updates and supports decentralized experimentation. Additionally, automated data provenance improves the transparency of experiment data, while PerQueue’s dependency management lays the groundwork for more complex and adaptive SDL workflows, including error handling, calibration, and cleaning processes. However, to generalize these advantages across different laboratories, ab initio codes, and platforms, some level of interoperability between workflow engines must be developed, as illustrated in Figure 1b. Such interoperability would enable research groups to adopt dynamic workflows without being locked into a specific engine, promote the reuse of modular workflow components across systems, and generally foster collaboration between teams operating on different infrastructures. Furthermore, establishing interoperable standards would support the long-term maintainability and portability of SDL workflows, allowing the scientific community to ease the sharing of methodologies and avoid the fragmentation of tools and expertise across isolated silos.

Beyond the scope of an individual SDL workflow, a modular and flexible orchestrator integrated across methodologies could improve integration efficiency and data alignment in collaborative and federated research efforts. Given the complexity of MAPs, integrating reusable workflow modules will be essential for scalable implementation. The flexibility offered by PerQueue supports the creation of complex, multi-modal/method workflows in both SDLs and optimization frameworks. However, adhering to the FAIR principles [52] in MAP campaigns remains a challenge, particularly when dealing with heterogeneous data sources, distributed methods, and local data storage constraints. Streamlined interoperable work-

flow managers like PerQueue have the potential to improve data provenance, increase transparency, and enhance interoperability between software systems.

To fully unlock their potential, advanced MAPs will require parallel AI agents capable of running optimizations campaigns simultaneously. In addition to handling multi-objective optimization challenges, optimizers must account for variations in data acquisition time across multi-fidelity methods and the associated costs. Parallel validation models could further improve the reliability by re-requesting critical data points when models become overly dependent on individual data points. Such interconnected decision-making frameworks will not be possible without robust workflow systems capable of scaling with expanding datasets and methodologies, while dynamically adapting the execution path on-the-fly. As MAP infrastructures grow, ensuring scalability and efficiency in workflow management will be a critical challenge.

Advancing dynamic workflows in MAPs will accelerate materials design, including for catalysts, batteries, semiconductors, etc. However, achieving this requires technological advancements and cross-disciplinary collaboration. Interoperable data infrastructures with well-defined standards are essential for large-scale projects, demanding coordinated efforts from experimentalists, computational researchers, and industry stakeholders as demonstrated in [43]. Additionally, integrating large-scale facilities into MAPs requires clear data management strategies, as full data sharing is often impractical [53]. While FINALES has made progress toward modular, problem-agnostic MAP infrastructures [12], broader community-driven efforts are needed to enhance scalability and deployment.

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Code Availability

- The controller module for the color mixing platform and the PerQueue workflow for optimizing to a target color is available at https://github.com/dtu-energy/color_mixing_pumpbot.
- The Odyssey package for performing Bayesian Optimization experiments is available at <https://github.com/dtu-energy/Odyssey>
- The PerQueue repository <https://gitlab.com/asm-dtu/perqueue>

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We assess the maturity and integration readiness of key methodologies for Materials Acceleration Platforms (MAPs), highlighting the need for dynamic workflow managers. Demonstrating this, we integrate PerQueue into a color-mixing robot, showing how flexible orchestration improves coordination and optimization. Our results underscore the importance of modular workflows for scalable, FAIR-compliant self-driving laboratories.